

THE ESSENCE OF THE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF
CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE
CONDITIONS OF MODERNIZATION OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the content and essence of the innovative development of construction materials industrial enterprises in the conditions of the development of the national economy, as well as the views of scientists.*

Key words. *Innovation, innovative process, production, modernization, national economy, transformation, competence.*

R. Foster and S. Kaplan, based on the analysis of the results of the data obtained during the research of the conditions of market efficiency of large American companies, from the point of view of innovation, implementation results and the level of uncertainty (risk value) in the process of their development and implementation. developed a law reflecting "quantitative" differences between types. According to them, this law is that significant innovation processes cause much more changes than evolutionary innovations, which in turn cause similar changes in the financial state of the market. but in this process the value at risk increases by 10 times.

Transformational innovations tend to have a greater scope by disrupting the

market structure more effectively than evolutionary innovations compared to substantive innovations. Thus, the scale of evaluation of innovative processes will have a logarithmic character - ten important evolutionary innovations for every hundred evolutionary innovations, and one transformative innovation for every ten important innovations. In addition, transformational innovations are considered very active, that is, they appear as a source of potential changes that are not yet visible at a given time.

Currently, all types of innovations are considered in detail in the guidance document of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). The main difference between this guide and previous editions is that it provides for the expansion of types of possible innovations in the field of material production. In addition to the two types of technological product and process innovations considered earlier, the developers of innovations recognize the need to include two more types of non-technological innovations - marketing and organizational innovations.

Based on the above-mentioned interpretations and classifications of the concept of innovation, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that innovation is considered in terms of technology, commerce, social systems, and relations with economic development. In this case, it is assumed that the innovation should be directed to the market requirements, but there will be less connections with marketing.

An interesting study of successful innovative products carried out in the USA showed that about 80% of products originate from ideas created by market demands. And in Great Britain, research conducted within the framework of SAPPHO confirmed that one of the main factors of success is meeting the needs of the market. Representatives of the world-famous Hewlett-Packard company

believe that understanding the needs of the market is the main factor of product success.

Since one of the main properties of innovations is their feasibility from a commercial point of view, that is, their delivery to the consumer, it is necessary to dwell on this aspect more widely.

The analysis of the scientific literature allows us to draw a conclusion that the basic (basic) innovation means that the consumer did not have "consumer competence" at a certain time, and as a result of the introduction of the innovation It can be said that innovation creates situations that change consumer stereotypes. Innovations that cause a change in consumption in a slightly smaller way, but have a number of useful properties (properties, price, etc.) for the consumer can be counted as an improving innovation. If the value of innovation is low for the consumer, then it can be called modernizing. But nevertheless, the desired innovation not only helps to increase the interest of consumers in the product, but also helps to open new markets in the conditions that this innovation is sufficiently new.

According to the data, fundamentally new goods account for 8-9% of all innovations, and most innovations are modified types of existing goods or modifications of production methods.

The perspective on the problem of limiting innovation and imitation in innovative activity is also interesting. According to O. Shankar's research, imitations play an important role in innovative development. Virtually 98% of the value created by innovation is provided by imitators. Almost 75% of the 48 innovations studied by them turned out to be imitations, and with the acceleration of scientific and technical progress, the time between an innovation and its imitation was reduced to almost a year. The imitators were able to create promising

innovative ideas almost three times cheaper and faster due to careful study and understanding of the essence of the "basic structure" of innovations. For example, McDonald's was able to take a copy of the WhiteCastle system, which was the first in the field of fast food restaurants, and even surpassed it in terms of sales.

It can be concluded that many patents envisage the development of the original invention, and in the conditions that most products, processes, methods and ideas are not protected by patents, enterprises copy the part of the innovation that benefits them, based on the development and improvement of their innovation. it is desirable for them to use imitation, which allows them to create their products.

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